

Dual Reference Genomes from F1 Hybrids: Phased Assembly of North African Catfish and Bighead Catfish with Hi-C Data

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ABSTRACT

The present study reports the haplotype-resolved genome assembly of a Thai F1 hybrid catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*), an allodiploid produced by crossing Thai bighead catfish (*C. macrocephalus*) and North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*). In aquaculture, where selective breeding program success relies on high-quality genome assemblies, the combination of high species divergence (10%) and differential heterozygosity (1.56% and 0.521%) between parental genomes often results in fragmented and partially phased assemblies, complicating breeding efforts. This study demonstrates that haplotype separation in F1 hybrid genomes can be achieved despite 10% cross-species nucleotide divergence using PacBio HiFi, ONT Nanopore, Illumina PE, and Hi-C chromatin interaction data. Hifiasm Hi-C was used for building the assembly, while HapHiC enabled its spatial scaffolding into chromosomes and accurate separation of parental assemblies from Hi-C long-range interactions, resulting in two fully phased, chromosome-length haploid-complete genomes. The final diploid genome assembly comprises 27 pseudochromosomes for *C. macrocephalus* and 28 for *C. gariepinus*, collectively spanning 1.8 Gb with median log-scaled assembly base error quality values of 50 to 60. The assembly is 99.4% complete based on k-mer analysis (k=21 and k=31) and 97% complete according to the BUSCO criterion, despite low initial sequencing coverage (4–5X ONT and <10X HiFi) after read-to-genome mapping. Of the 55 pseudochromosomes, eight have achieved telomere-to-telomere continuity, with the majority of the remaining chromosomes demonstrating near completion.

Significance

Despite frequent natural hybridization, no standard genome assembly pipeline exists for teleost F1 genomes. Our study demonstrates that high-resolution, haplotype-resolved assemblies can be generated from a single F1 individual, recovering clean, phased parental genomes without phylogenetic background noise from inter-haplotype mixing. This provides a powerful platform for phylogenomic analysis, structural comparisons, and trait mapping in systems where parental species are rare, extinct, or genetically inaccessible. Our comprehensive approach produces two highly complete, chromosome-scale reference genomes with telomere-to-telomere continuity despite high heterozygosity (10%) and teleost genome complexity. This cost-effective strategy is particularly valuable for selective breeding programs or when parental species are unavailable, yielding fully phased, normalized parental genomes from a single F1 individual.

Introduction

This study presents the first chromosome-level, haplotype-resolved assembly for the Thai F1 hybrid catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*), generating two high-quality reference genomes that support aquaculture hybridization programs in Southeast Asia. The Thai bighead catfish (*C. macrocephalus*) and the North African catfish (*C. gariepinus*) are economically important species commonly hybridized to improve growth performance and disease resistance in aquaculture.

Here, we sequenced an F1 hybrid individual to elucidate its genome structure and composition using a multi-platform sequencing strategy combining Illumina short reads¹, Hi-C proximity ligation reads^{2,3}, PacBio HiFi long reads⁴, and Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) reads⁵. This approach enabled reconstruction of two fully phased⁶, non-homotypic parental genomes, without requiring the two parental sequencing data⁷, comprising 27 pseudochromosomes for *C. macrocephalus* and 28 for *C. gariepinus*. The observed heterozygosity rate (10%) reflects the high genomic divergence between parental species, encompassing both single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and structural variants (SVs).

Despite challenges such as high species divergence, extensive repeat content (35%), and pronounced heterozygosity, our integrated strategy successfully applied chromatin interaction data clustering methods⁸ and produced assemblies with reference-grade structural accuracy and completeness using relatively low sequencing depths (4–5× for ONT and <10× for HiFi). These assemblies outperform previous non-hybrid assemblies for *C. macrocephalus* (NCBI BioSample: [SAMN42347118](#)), providing essential genomic resources for future breeding, phylogenetic, and comparative genomics studies.

Results

DNA Sequencing of F1 Hybrid Catfish

We sequenced the F1 hybrid catfish to elucidate its genome structure and composition using a multi-platform strategy (**Figure 1**). A representative photography of a F1 hybrid catfish is shown in **Figure 2A**. We performed a GenomeScope2.0 analysis to survey the genome from raw DNA sequence data before assembly⁹, which estimated a diploid genome size of approximately 1.8 Gb and a haploid genome size of 904 Mb with a heterozygosity rate of 10.1%, reflecting the divergence between *C. macrocephalus* and *C. gariepinus* (**Figure 1A**)⁹. **Figure 1B** shows the sequencing coverage across platforms. Illumina paired-end sequencing achieved 36× coverage with high base quality (92% ≥ Q30), and Hi-C libraries provided 40× coverage with >97% ≥ Q30, enabling chromosome-scale scaffolding and phasing. PacBio HiFi sequencing achieved 13× coverage with a read N50 of 10 kb and mean Q28.7, while ONT sequencing produced 36× coverage with a read N50 of 4 kb and median Q11, though only 10× were usable due to high error rates. **Figure 1C** shows the distribution of HiFi read lengths and their mean PHRED quality scores, which were mostly above Q30, indicating high base accuracy suitable for assembly. **Figure 1D** shows ONT read lengths spanning a wide range, including ultra-long reads exceeding 100 kb, with mean PHRED quality scores ranging between Q10 and Q15. Together, these datasets provided high-accuracy HiFi reads for contig construction, ultra-long ONT reads for scaffolding, and Illumina and Hi-C data for polishing and chromosome-scale phasing, enabling a highly contiguous and complete assembly of both parental subgenomes.

A Near Telomere-To-Telomere Genome Assembly For F1 Hybrid Catfish

Overview and Assembly Architecture Our results demonstrate that robust assembly pipelines can successfully handle complex and highly heterozygous F1 diploid genomes when haplotype resolution is prioritized from the outset. **Figure 2C** show the in-silico karyotype after de novo haplotype-resolved assembly of F1 hybrid catfish, it features a total of 55 Hi-C scaffolds, comprising 27 pseudochromosomes for *C. macrocephalus* and 28 for *C. gariepinus*, corresponding to the 55 chromosomes expected in F1 hybrid catfish. These results are corroborated by previous karyotype studies performed in bighead catfish, North African catfish and their F1 offspring¹⁰.

Global Assembly Metrics The F1 Hybrid Catfish (fClahyb - CGAF) assembly was split into two separate subgenomes and released to GenBank, consisting of 55 scaffolds (all exceeding 10,000 bp) totaling 1,858,695,542 bp, plus one mtDNA sequence and zero unplaced sequences. The assembly achieved exceptional contiguity, with every contig in scaffolds exceeding 1,000,000 bp. The longest scaffold spans 51,692,840 bp and the second longest reaches 51,114,572 bp, both corresponding to telomere-to-telomere chromosomes (T2T, with 0 gaps). The assembly reached an N50 of 33,844,116 bp, indicating high contiguity. Read-to-contig HiFi minimap2 alignment, performed in the context of Inspector analysis¹¹, confirms a 99.96% mapping rate, a 0.52% split-read rate, and an average mapped depth of 10.65×, which remains consistent for contigs >1 Mbp. The final polished assembly achieved a QV of 50.28 (pileup-based, from HiFi read mapping), indicating robust base-level accuracy and structural integrity suitable for various downstream analyses.

Mitochondrial Genome One mitochondrial sequence, confirmed through IGV polymorphism analysis, belongs to *C. macrocephalus*, providing additional genomic context for the hybrid assembly.

High Gene Duplication Rates After Near-Complete and Error-Free Fully-phased Genome Assembly indicate a duplicated genome structure.

BUSCO Completeness in single orthologous genes shows high duplication rates, indicative of a duplicated genome structure. We assessed the completeness of the North African catfish, bighead catfish, and F1 hybrid catfish genome assemblies using BUSCO analysis with the Actinopterygii dataset comprising 3,640 conserved single-copy orthologous genes. The results are shown in **Figure 2B**. The North African catfish assembly contained 3,536 complete BUSCOs (97.1%), of which 3,485 were single-copy (95.7%) and 51 were duplicated (1.4%), with only 24 fragmented (0.7%) and 80 missing genes (2.2%). Similarly, the bighead catfish assembly recovered 3,518 complete BUSCOs (96.6%), including 3,470 single-copy (95.3%) and 48 duplicated (1.3%) genes, alongside 24 fragmented (0.7%) and 98 missing genes (2.7%). In contrast, the F1 hybrid catfish assembly, which contains both the North African catfish and bighead catfish subgenomes, showed a markedly different profile with 3,584 complete BUSCOs (98.5%), but only 317 in single copy (8.7%) and 3,267 present in duplicated form (89.8%), accompanied by 12 fragmented (0.3%) and 44 missing genes (1.2%). This exceptionally high proportion of duplicated BUSCOs in the hybrid genome indicates retention of both parental haplotypes, as distinct chromosome sets, consistent with its interspecific hybrid origin and uncollapsed diploid assembly.

Accurate Haplotype Resolution Confirms Distinct Haploid Parental Genomes

The absence of off-diagonal strong signals after Hi-C mapping confirms the recovery of 55 chromosomes. We also counted the total number of interactions between pairs of loci in the F1 hybrid catfish genome using proximity ligation (Hi-C) data. **Figure 2C** shows the Hi-C contact map of the 55 scaffolds, where each red square represents an individual pseudochromosome. The absence of off-diagonal strong signals indicates no inter-chromosomal misassemblies or rearrangements. Notably, faint diagonal lines connecting pairs of pseudochromosomes can be observed; these reflect weak Hi-C contacts between homologous chromosomes originating from the two different parental species (North African catfish vs. bighead catfish). This further supports that the genome has reached a state of accurate haplotype resolution, that each chromosome has a homologous counterpart in the other species, that the genome is structured into two sets of haploid chromosomes, and that chromosome number consistency (27 + 28) is maintained. Overall, these results confirm the accurate representation of both parental subgenomes, with each species' subgenome maintained as a distinct haploid set within the F1 hybrid genome.

K-mer analysis confirms accurate haplotype separation and absence of hybrid collapse. We counted k-mers from Illumina-HiFi whole-genome sequencing reads of the F1 hybrid catfish, as well as from each haplotype assembly, using Meryl within the Merqury pipeline¹². The distinct k-mer multiplicity spectrum plot produced by Merqury is shown in **Figure 2D**, it displays the distribution of k-mers (31 nucleotides in length) derived from both the raw sequencing reads and the F1 hybrid catfish assembly. This spectrum exhibits a clean bimodal distribution with peaks at 1× multiplicity (heterozygous k-mers present in a single copy per haplotype, seen at $x=30$ in the blue and red curves) and 2× multiplicity (homozygous k-mers present in both haplotypes, seen at $x=60$ in the green curve), characteristic of well-phased diploid assemblies. The small grey peak at the far left represents read-only k-mers absent from the assembly, indicating minimal missing data. The plot also shows that k-mers unique to each parental haplotype are assigned to either the *fClahyb_Gar-only* subgenome (North African catfish) or the *fClahyb_Mac-only* subgenome (bighead catfish), while shared k-mers cluster in the 2× peak, reflecting conserved regions between both parental genomes. Notably, there were no peaks above 2× multiplicity, indicating a lack of polyploidization or haplotype collapse. The absence of tertiary peaks (e.g., 3× or higher) further suggests minimal sequence redundancy and confirms high phasing accuracy.

Copy number analysis confirms that F1 hybrid genome has two haploid sets of chromosomes, one haploid set per parental species

Copy number spectrum confirms that the F1 hybrid genome has two haploid sets of chromosomes originating from two separate parental species. Continuing with the Merqury pipeline¹², we generated a resulting copy number spectrum ("spectra-cn") plot, presented in **Figure 2E**, which shows the multiplicity of each k-mer in the read set, colored by its copy number in the assembly. The Illumina dataset was sequenced at an average coverage of 60×, producing a dominant peak near $x=30$ corresponding to heterozygous 1-copy k-mers unique to each haplotype (red curve), and a smaller peak near $x=60$ reflecting homozygous 2-copy k-mers shared between subgenomes (blue curve). The 2-copy peak represents approximately 10% of k-mers, suggesting that 10% of the two parental genomes are identical, while the remaining 90% are haplotype-specific. No tertiary (3-copy, green curve), quaternary (4-copy, purple curve), or quinary (>4-copy, orange curve) peaks were observed,

indicating absence of polyploidization, chromosome duplications, copy number variation (CNV) multiplications, and confirming the assembly contains two divergent haploid sets without collapsed regions. Overall, this spectrum supports accurate haplotype separation, low redundancy, and high completeness of the F1 hybrid assembly.

Macrosynteny analysis reveals intact parental chromosome structure and potential suppression of meiotic recombination in F1 hybrid catfish

Macrosynteny analysis reveals intact parental chromosome structure and suppression of recombination, with high homology to pure parental species genomes. A synteny analysis was conducted across 2,003 single-copy BUSCO orthologs in five assemblies using *rbhXpress* (<https://github.com/SamiLh11/rbhXpress>) and *macrosyntR*¹³ software. The analysis, which included the two hybrid haplotypes and three Clariid species, confirmed the F1 hybrid nature of the genome (**Figure 2F**). The two parental species demonstrate clear separated subgenome-specific alignment: C.fHyb_Gar aligns exclusively with *Clarias gariepinus* (North African catfish; TaxID: 13013; GenBank accession number [JAMBPB000000000.1](#)), while C.fHyb_Mac aligns with *Clarias macrocephalus* (Bighead catfish; TaxID: 35657; GenBank accession number [JBLWMO000000000.1](#)). No evidence of chromosomal mixing, inter-haplotype rearrangements, or segmental exchanges was detected between subgenomes, indicating strict maintenance of parental chromosome architecture in the hybrid.

High Cross-Species Divergence Enables Near-Error-Free Haplotype Assembly

Mercury K-mer completeness in F1 genome, indicates near-complete recovery of the raw sequencing data. We conducted Mercury analysis¹² to evaluate assembly completeness by comparing k-mers derived from the raw sequencing reads to those present in the final assembly. The results showed k-mer completeness ranging from 99.4% (k=21) to 99.38% (k=31), confirming the high completeness of the F1 hybrid genome assembly. The bar at the origin of the plots in **Figure 2D** represents k-mers found only in the assembly. From these k-mers, we can estimate an assembly consensus quality value (QV), which represents a log-scaled probability of error for the consensus base calls (see¹² for methods). Higher QVs indicate a more accurate consensus, where Q30 corresponds to 99.9% accuracy, Q40 to 99.99%, etc. **Table 1** shows data of nucleotide accuracy in F1 genome which achieved a median QV of 55 (Mercury analysis¹²), it provides detailed scaffold metrics including quality values, error counts, and telomere-to-telomere status. Consensus Quality Values (QVs) for the hybrid genome and each sub-genome were 50.1, 48.3, and 49.5, respectively, with k-mer completeness scores of 96.7%, 95.8%, and 97.4% for hybrid (2 haps, combined), bighead, and North African catfish sub-genomes. North African catfish scaffolds consistently exhibited higher QV values (up to 65.79) compared to bighead catfish scaffolds (50-54 range), with several chromosomes achieving complete T2T continuity with no gaps and a single scaffold for a chromosome. Overall, the polished assembly achieved a QV of 50.28 (pileup-based, from HiFi read mapping in Inspector v1.3¹¹), indicating a robust base-level accuracy and structural integrity suitable for various types of downstream analyses.

The chromosome structures are near-perfect in quality and show few large-scale errors after assembly. **Table 2** presents structural accuracy metrics from CRAQ analysis¹⁴, showing North African catfish scaffolds displayed near-perfect Structural Assembly Quality Index (S-AQI) and Regional Assembly Quality Index (R-AQI), both ranging approximately from 97% to 100%, indicating minimal misassemblies at both the large-scale and regional-scale levels. In contrast, bighead catfish scaffolds exhibited slightly lower accuracy, with S-AQI values around 90–97% and R-AQI between 90–96%. This reduction in quality may be attributed to factors such as lower species heterozygosity, increased local assembly complexity due to transposable element (TE) content, or potential issues in sequencing quality, possibly arising from degraded genomic DNA used in ONT sequencing.

Suppression of Cross-Species Recombination Maintains Parental Genome Integrity in F1 Hybrid Catfish

Synteny and structural variation comparisons between the F1 hybrid genome and its parental species revealed limited large-scale rearrangements within each subgenome and no evidence of recombination between them.

Structural variation analysis within the F1 hybrid catfish assembly confirms absence of cross-species recombination. Structural validation of the F1 hybrid catfish pseudochromosomes using Inspector software¹¹ identified 22 large-scale structural variants (>50 bp), comprising 12 expansions, 7 collapses, only 2–5 haplotype switch errors (small regions where nucleotides were switched between homologous chromosomes, likely due to assembly misjoins and not homologous recombination during meiosis), and 1 inversion. In total, 8,897 small-scale base-level errors were detected (4.79 per Mb), including 6,226 substitutions, 1,189 expansions, and 1,482 collapses. The final polished assembly achieved a base-level QV of 50.28 based on HiFi read pileups redistributed across the 55 pseudochromosomes, indicating high sequence accuracy suitable for downstream genomic

analyses.

Structural variation analysis against pure parental species reference genomes confirms absence of cross-species recombination. To evaluate large-scale structural integrity and potential cross-species recombination within the F1 hybrid genome, we aligned each parental assembly to its respective hybrid subgenome using `minimap2` with the `-eqx` flag to produce base-level alignment CIGAR strings. Structural variation and synteny were inferred using `SyRI`, which identifies inversions, translocations, duplications, unaligned regions, and other rearrangements relative to syntenic blocks. Visualisation was performed with `plotsr`. **Figure 3** presents the North African catfish subgenome comparison (reference: GCA_024256425.2_CGAR_prim_01v2_genomic; query: GCA_048129225.1_fClaHyb_Gar_genomic). Syntenic regions covered 886 Mb (90.91%) of the genome, with 9 Mb (0.93%) inverted, 6.5 Mb (0.67%) translocated, 3 Mb (0.31%) duplicated in the query, and 2.2 Mb (0.23%) duplicated in the reference. Unaligned query regions totaled 59.5 Mb (6.10%), while unaligned reference regions summed to 60 Mb (6.16%). Sequence variation analysis identified 7,182,606 SNPs, 786,715 insertions spanning 10.6 Mb, and 762,532 deletions spanning 10.5 Mb. Highly diverged regions (regions with higher SNP densities than average) accounted for approximately 254 Mb, or 26% of the genome.

Figure 4 shows the Bighead catfish subgenome comparison (reference: GCA_048544425.1_fClaMac1.0_hap1_genomic; query: GCA_048129245.1_fClaHyb_Mac_genomic). Here, syntenic regions spanned 832 Mb (94.55%), with 2.9 Mb (0.32%) inverted, 7.2 Mb (0.82%) translocated, 3.6 Mb (0.41%) duplicated in the query, and 2.7 Mb (0.30%) duplicated in the reference. Unaligned query regions totaled 50.8 Mb (5.77%) and unaligned reference regions 33.5 Mb (3.81%). Sequence variation analysis revealed 2,940,699 SNPs, 585,243 insertions covering 10.5 Mb, and 581,006 deletions covering 11.4 Mb. Highly diverged regions comprised approximately 92 Mb, or 10.9% of the genome. Together, these results demonstrate extensive preservation of parental chromosome structures within the hybrid assembly and confirm the absence of inter-subgenome recombination events.

Evolutionary and applied implications

Our results suggest the absence of homologous recombination between parental chromosomes in the F1 hybrid catfish genome. **Figure 5** illustrates our conceptual model, where F1 hybrids retain two unmixed haploid subgenomes, functioning as genetic reservoirs of parental alleles. Supporting evidence includes the clean k-mer multiplicity spectra, showing distinct haplotype-specific peaks without intermediate multiplicities (**Figure 2D**), genome-wide synteny analyses demonstrating strict parental chromosome preservation (**Figure 2F**), and Hi-C contact maps confirming accurate chromosome separation without off-diagonal signals (**Figure 2C**).

Our small model hypothesizes that recombination outcomes in F1 hybrids depend on parental sequence divergence. In highly divergent crosses (>5–10% nucleotide divergence), structural differences and incompatibilities hinder synapsis during meiosis I, suppressing recombination entirely, as observed here. Conversely, crossing over may occur in more closely related species if divergence permits synapsis. However, limitations in sample size prevent generalization of this hypothesis to all F1 hybrid catfish or other teleost hybrids. Functionally, F1 hybrids often exhibit heterosis—enhanced growth, resilience, and fertility compared to parental lines—driven by transcriptional, post-transcriptional, and proteomic regulation rather than genomic DNA recombination¹⁵.

Discussion

F1 hybrid genomes and pure (F0) high-quality, near-chromosome-scale reference genomes represent fundamental resources in aquaculture genomics. F0 genomes provide accurate representations of individual species with annotated gene coordinates and structural features, while F1 hybrid genomes capture both parental haplotypes within a single assembly, enabling direct comparison of inherited genomic segments. The assembly of F1 hybrid genomes is particularly challenging due to their high heterozygosity, cross-species haplotype variation, and abundant repetitive transposable elements (TEs), all of which hinder phased assembly without parental allele mixing. These difficulties affect highly heterozygous F1 catfish genomes and extend to other complex systems, including low-heterozygosity species like bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) and polyploid organisms such as F1 *Arabidopsis thaliana* hybrids¹². Traditional assembly approaches often collapse haplotypes or produce incorrectly phased assemblies, limiting their utility for downstream applications.

Recent technological advances have made high-quality F1 hybrid genome assembly increasingly feasible. F1 hybrid genomes can now be successfully assembled using advanced single-molecule DNA sequencing technologies and sophisticated computational approaches. The integration of proximity ligation data (Hi-C)¹⁶ with HiFi sequencing⁴, combined

with cutting-edge assembly algorithms such as HapHiC⁸ and Hifiasm⁶, enables the generation of phased, highly accurate genome representations. Together, these methodologies produce phased assemblies with synchronized SNPs relative to each parental genome and minimal structural variation errors, though at considerable computational and financial costs. F1 hybrid genomes have been successfully assembled in several vertebrate organisms, demonstrating the broad applicability of genome assembly methods. Notable examples include near-complete assemblies of both parental genomes from *Silurus asotus* × *S. meridionalis* hybrids¹⁷, highly continuous yak-cattle (*Bos grunniens* × *Bos taurus*) assemblies generated through trio binning¹⁸, and ultracontinuous haploid genomes from Bengal hybrid cats (*Felis catus* × *Prionailurus bengalensis*)¹⁹. However, standardized methodologies for teleost fishes—organisms that frequently hybridize in natural populations—have remained limited due to challenges in handling highly heterozygous genomes and the complex repetitive landscapes characteristic of fish genomes.

Here, we demonstrated that Q60+ high-quality genome assembly from highly heterozygous F1 individuals is achievable using relatively low-coverage 3rd-generation sequencing data when assembly workflows are specifically adapted to genome complexity, including genome size, chromosome number, and ploidy. We presented the successful dual haplotype-resolved reference genomes for North African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and bighead catfish (*C. macrocephalus*) assembled from a single F1 hybrid individual (*Clarias gariepinus* × *C. macrocephalus*). This work establishes a cost-effective methodology for generating high-quality genomic resources while providing immediately useful reference genomes for catfish aquaculture and a reproducible framework for F1 hybrid genome assembly in other systems.

Methods

Genome Assembly and Quality Assessment Workflow

The complete workflow for generating chromosome-scale assemblies of the Thai F1 hybrid catfish is presented in **Figure 2**. The workflow consists of six sequential steps (from 1A to step 6) that integrate multiple sequencing technologies and analysis tools and pipelines in specific order used to achieve optimal phasing and Hi-C scaffolding at a high-contiguity, low structural error rate, high solve rates, and high base-accuracy genome assemblies in highly heterozygous F1 genomes. Below, we outline each step in detail.

- **Step 1: DNA Sequencing, Genome Survey, and k-mer Meryl Databases** Genomic DNA was extracted from the liver tissue of a single F1 hybrid individual using a custom protocol²⁰. Sex was determined to be female based on histology and external gonadal examination^{21,22}. Sequencing was performed using four complementary platforms generating four synergistic raw sequencing data types: (i) Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) High-Fidelity (HiFi) sequencing⁴ for generating highly accurate contigs, (ii) Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) long-read sequencing⁵ for scaffolding and resolving repetitive regions, and (iii and iv) Illumina short-read 150 base paired-end sequencing (Hi-C, and standard non Hi-C)¹ for chromosomal phasing and error correction, respectively. Genome survey aims in assessing genome characteristics (genome size, heterozygosity, repeat content) from raw sequencing data (e.g., Illumina short-reads) using k-mer analysis in Jellyfish²³ and GenomeScope2.0⁹. K-mer Meryl databases use 21-mer and 31-mer DNA strings to support quality evaluation and error correction in genome assemblies. The shorter 21-mer spectra provide high sensitivity for detecting potential errors, while the longer 31-mer spectra offer higher specificity, validating true variants and minimizing false positives. During genome polishing, these k-mer databases enhance effective coverage in low-depth HiFi regions by leveraging k-mer spectra to guide targeted corrections and improve assembly accuracy. Meryl databases (N=2) consisted in 21-mer and 31-mer hybrid k-mer databases (`hybrid.hifi.illuminaPCRfree.gt1.db.meryl`), made from combined Illumina and HiFi reads using Meryl¹², as explained in the T2T-polish GitHub repository (<https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>)²⁴.
- **Step 2: Contig Assembly and Their Haplotype Phasing** Contig assembly was performed using Hifiasm⁶, a haplotype-resolved assembler integrating data from HiFi reads, Hi-C reads, and ONT reads. This resulted in two haplotype-separated subgenomes (*hap1* and *hap2*). However, we observed that the Hifiasm algorithm artificially deduplicated the primary phased haplotype assembly, producing two redundant copies, namely `.hic.hap1.p_ctg.fa` and `.hic.hap2.p_ctg.fa` which were nearly identical (combined genome size of 3.6Gb versus expected 1.8Gb, GenomeScope2.0). The best strategy was therefore to cluster parental haplotigs (i.e., the haplotype-specific contigs also referred to as "unitigs", contained in the haplotype-resolved polished unitig graph without small bubbles) prior to performing additional scaffolding and phasing. After, Hifiasm, the initial genome graph in GFA format was fragmented, containing over 1661 polished unitigs (`P_utg.gfa`). To resolve these issues, we used polished unitigs instead of primary contigs as input for HapHiC⁸. In brief, to prepare for HapHiC, in situ Hi-C data was aligned to the Hifiasm draft genome assembly (`P_utg.gfa`) using BWA designed for Hi-C data (i.e., setting `5SP`), results were Hi-C read alignments in SAM file format²⁵, these were pre-filtered to allow a mapping quality of 1 (MAPQ1) (i.e., for the best

Hi-C match only) with Samtools view²⁶ and with a maximum of two mutations allowed per Hi-C read alignment (i.e., edit distance $NM \leq 2$) with Samblaster²⁷. HapHiC was used to error-correct, anchor, order and orient the pieces in the Hifiasm polished unitig assembly. The HapHiC method performs an initial clustering of unitigs based on their haplotype assignment in Hifiasm. Settings were `remove_allelic_links 2` (to account for genome diploidy), and defining 55 chromosomes as the expected karyotype¹⁰. Results of combining Hifiasm Hi-C and HapHiC for our highly heterozygous F1 genome (10% heterozygosity, GenomeScope2.0) successfully scaffolded and phased the unitig assembly on the first attempt, reduced the number of gaps and increased solve rate and resulted in very high assembly quality metrics and success, achieving intermediate results of >99.2% k-mer completeness, 55 scaffolds (i.e., pseudochromosomes), >97% BUSCO completeness, an our expected genome size of 1.8 Gb, and only 1–2 switch errors after assembly quality assessment with Inspector¹¹.

- **Step 3: Hi-C Scaffold Pseudo-Molecules Processing and Pseudochromosome Validation** Initially, chromosome-scale assemblies were not processed and validated using CRAQ¹⁴, a software which identifies large-scale structural errors (i.e., false inversions, false translocations) within pseudochromosomes, finds breakpoints in the problematic contigs, and split the misassembly junctions prior performing pseudo-molecule construction and manual refinement (i.e., manual-review). We directly used Hifiasm output for Hi-C scaffolding and manual review of Hi-C scaffolds in Juicebox Assembly Tools aka JBAT / Juicebox^{2,16}. Juicebox was used for manual Hi-C scaffold review, resolution of misjoins and structural artifacts. For more information on the manual-review in JBAT, please see <https://www.dnazoo.org/methods>. In brief, HapHiC generated `.assembly` and `.hic` data files for visualization and manual curation of Hi-C scaffolds in Juicebox, these files were automatically created using the 3D-DNA visualization module, in conjunction with Juicer Tools, which resulted in `.hic` contact maps for the draft and the final genome assemblies. As a rule, apart from the initial HapHiC which used `.gfa` from Hifiasm, we always used CRAQ prior for FASTA assembly correction prior to manual review step using JBAT, which was employed to polish the genome assembly output by HapHiC and further polishing steps (see below).
- **Step 4: Structural and Base-Level Polishing** In several cases the many different types of draft assemblies were used as the starting point to improve gaps, structure and contiguity of the "HapHiC" F1 hybrid catfish assembly. These were both originating from the same assembly data (GreenHill, Flye, Hifiasm), or eventually from reference genomes of *Clarias gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2) and *C. macrocephalus* (unpublished) which were also used for comparative analysis, aiding in structural validation. Additional assembly was performed through Flye²⁸ and GreenHill²⁹. Haplotype-specific primary contigs from Hifiasm (`.hic.hap1.p_ctg.fa` and `.hic.hap2.p_ctg.fa`) were scaffolded using GreenHill²⁹, integrating Hi-C, Illumina, HiFi and ONT reads and Flye to generate extra solutions to better resolve structural variations, gaps, and highly repetitive elements such as satellite DNA. Large structural variants were corrected using Unimap³⁰ (Unimap, available at <https://github.com/lh3/unimap>) and Sniffles2³¹, identifying and resolving insertions, deletions, and rearrangements. Base-level polishing was performed iteratively using Clair3³² for small variant correction and Merfin³³ for error filtering, ensuring high-confidence base calls and correcting sequencing errors.
- **Step 5: Final Genome Refinement and Quality Assessment** Final quality assessment included quality values (QV) estimated using Merqury¹², with QV scores calculated at a k-mer size of k=21 and k=31 from their respective 21-mer and 31-mer hybrid k-mer databases (see above), BUSCO³⁴ was used to assess gene completeness with the Actinopterygii_odb10 database. Inspector software¹¹ estimated base-level accuracy and error rates using read pileups. The final curated genome achieved **QV60+** with 99.4% k-mer completeness, structured into chromosome-scale scaffolds comprising 55 pseudochromosomes. The mitochondrial genome was assembled by mapping ONT read data and Illumina data (as PacBio HiFi reads are less effective at capturing circular genomes due to adapter binding limitations) to reference (NC_046749.1) bighead catfish mtDNA, available at NCBI Nucleotide. All assembly FASTA sequences were prepared for public submission to GenBank, along with assembly metrics supporting this work: To ensure data quality and standardization, scaffold names were updated according to the Vertebrate Genome Project (VGP) naming conventions³⁵, next we used the NCBI's Foreign Contamination Screen (FCS) tool³⁶ to verify the absence of contaminants.

Additional methods, including DNA sequencing, read preparation, and assembly benchmarking, along with their corresponding results, are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

Data Records

Genome Assembly of F1 Hybrid Catfish (isolate:CGAF) – Bighead catfish (TaxID: 35657) and North African catfish (TaxID: 13013) subgenomes. GenBank accession numbers: [JBLWFY000000000](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/JBLWFY000000000), [JBLWFZ000000000](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/JBLWFZ000000000). Data records are hosted under

NCBI BioProject number ([PRJNA1153495](#)), and the F1 hybrid catfish (TaxID: 1334085) BioSample accession number is ([SAMN43395848](#)). Raw sequenced reads are hosted at NCBI SRA for different sequencing types: Nanopore ([SRR30599638](#)), HiFi ([SRR30599641](#)), Illumina ([SRR30599640](#)), and Hi-C ([SRR30599639](#)). The assembled genome, deposited as a whole-genome sequence (WGS) diploid assembly, designates parental samples *C. macrocephalus* as haplotype 1 and *C. gariepinus* BioSample accession number ([SAMN46907808](#) and [SAMN46730924](#) as haplotype 2. **Illumina non-Hi-C sequencing data for two additional BioSamples (different bloodlines)** was submitted for female *C. macrocephalus* at BioSample accession number ([SAMN42503781](#)) and for male *C. gariepinus* at BioSample accession number ([SAMN43548335](#)).

Usage Notes

Initial assembly data can be obtained from the Zenodo project repository (DOI [zenodo.14864261](#)). Collapsed-assembly data from Flye (CGAF_Flye.assembly.fasta), phased-assembly data from GreenHill (out_ConsensusOutput.fa), and initial haplotype-resolved polished unitig data from Hifiasm (CGA_HIC_UL.asm.hic.p_utg.fa) can all be mapped onto *C. macrocephalus* or *C. gariepinus* GenBank-submitted genomes using the Unimap command (unimap -cx asm5 -cs -t \$threads -a | samtools view -bhS -F4 -@ \$threads | samtools sort -@ \$threads -o unimap.sorted.bam). Raw sequencing long reads (PacBio HiFi and ONT) can be mapped using either Winnowmap (-ax map-pb/map-ont) or Minimap2 (-ax map-hifi/map-ont -secondary=no).

Code availability

No custom software or codes were developed as part of this research. All bioinformatics tools and pipelines were executed following the manual and protocols provided by the respective software developers. The versions of the software used, along with their corresponding parameters, have been thoroughly described in the Methods section.

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Author contributions statement

Genome assembly, analysis and data submissions were performed by Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres who also fully drafted the Manuscript. DNA sample preparation and sequencing outsourcing was managed by Dr. Worapong Singchat. Project conceptualization, supervision, and funding was led by Dr. Kornorn Srikulnath.

Competing interests

The corresponding author, Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres, certifies on behalf of all authors that there are no competing interests in this project. Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres joined the AGB research unit after the DNA sample preparation step. The research is solely aimed at improving aquaculture practices and outcomes.

Figures & Tables

Main Manuscript:

- **Figure 1:** Sequencing data summary for the F1 catfish genome assembly. (A) GenomeScope2.0 k-mer profile estimating genome size, heterozygosity, and repeat content. (B) Table summarizing sequencing protocols, coverage, and mapped read depth ranges. (C) HiFi read length versus mean PHRED quality score distribution, colored by GC content. (D) ONT read length versus mean PHRED quality score distribution, colored by GC content.
- **Figure 2:** Overview of F1 Hybrid Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* × *Clarias macrocephalus*) genome assembly validation. (A) Representative photograph of F1 hybrid catfish. (B) BUSCO completeness analysis showing high duplication rates indicative of dual subgenomes. (C) Hi-C contact map of 55 scaffolds confirming accurate chromosome separation. (D) K-mer multiplicity spectrum showing clean bimodal distribution. (E) Copy number spectrum confirming two haploid chromosome sets. (F) Macrosynteny analysis demonstrating intact parental chromosome structures.
- **Table 1:** Summary of scaffold metrics in the haplotype-resolved genome assembly of *Clarias macrocephalus* × *C. gariepinus*. Metrics include Quality Values (QV) from Merqury (k=21 and k=31), telomere orientation from QuarTeT, and gap counts from Detgaps.
- **Figure 3:** North African catfish subgenome synteny and structural variation summary. Reference: GCA_024256425.2; Query: GCA_048129225.1_fClaHyb_Gar_genomic. Bar plots summarize SNP, insertion, deletion, and structural variant counts and genome fractions.
- **Figure 4:** Bighead catfish subgenome synteny and structural variation summary. Reference: GCA_048544425.1; Query: GCA_048129245.1_fClaHyb_Mac_genomic. Bar plots summarize SNP, insertion, deletion, and structural variant counts and genome fractions.
- **Figure 5:** Conceptual framework of F1 hybrid catfish genome structure and its role in population restoration. The diagram illustrates pure parental species (F0) with high genome divergence (>5%) producing F1 hybrids via hybridization. F1 hybrids retain unmixed haploid subgenomes, function as genetic reservoirs of parental alleles, and exhibit heterosis driven by gene dosage and morphogen gradient effects.

- **Figure 6:** Workflow for Genome Assembly and Quality Assessment of the F1 Hybrid Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* × *C. macrocephalus*). This figure outlines the complete workflow for assembling the F1 hybrid catfish genome, highlighting the progenitor species and quality metrics achieved at each key assembly step.

Supplementary Materials:

- **Table S1:** Summary of structural accuracy metrics of scaffolds in the haplotype-resolved genome assembly. Structural accuracy (S-AQI, %), Regional accuracy (R-AQI %), and heterozygous regions (Avg.CSH/Avg.CRH) from CRAQ analysis.
- **Figure S1:** F1 Hybrid Catfish Genome Card and Global Assembly Metrics.
- **Figure S2:** GenomeScope 2.0 profiles for parental species and F1 hybrid catfish. Combined analysis showing heterozygosity and genome size estimates based on k-mer sizes k=21 and k=31, demonstrating ~10% inter-species divergence in the hybrid and species-specific heterozygosity levels.
- **Figure S3:** Assembly validation and QV improvement through manual curation. (A) Chromosome 03 showing QV improvement after iterative polishing rounds. (B) Chromosome 02 demonstrating identification and correction of a false duplication event.
- **Figure S4:** F1 hybrid catfish assembly progress over one year (January 2024 – November 2024), illustrating gap closure and telomere recovery through iterative manual curation.
- **Figure S5:** Hi-C interaction maps for North African catfish subgenome. Individual contact matrices for all 28 pseudochromosomes showing strong diagonal patterns confirming high assembly contiguity.
- **Figure S6:** Hi-C interaction maps for bighead catfish subgenome. Individual contact matrices for all 27 pseudochromosomes demonstrating successful chromosome-scale assembly and haplotype resolution.

Figure 1. Sequencing data summary for the F1 catfish genome assembly. (A) GenomeScope2.0 k-mer profile estimating genome size, heterozygosity, and repeat content. (B) Table summarising sequencing protocols, coverage, and mapped read depth ranges. (C) HiFi read length versus mean PHRED quality score distribution, coloured by GC content. (D) ONT read length versus mean PHRED quality score distribution, coloured by GC content. Together, these panels illustrate raw read quality, length distributions, and k-mer-based genome characteristics underlying the assembly.

Figure 2. Overview of F1 Hybrid Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus* × *Clarias macrocephalus*) genome assembly validation. Hi-C phasing confirms 55 pseudochromosomes, with BUSCO scores indicating 97% gene completeness. Synteny analysis and k-mer distributions support the F1 hybrid nature, demonstrating chromosome separation into subgenomes and their evolutionary affiliations.

Table 1. Summary of scaffold metrics in the false haplotype-resolved genome assembly of *Clarias macrocephalus* x *C. gariepinus*. Metrics include Quality Values (QV) from Merquy (k=21 and k=31 meryl readmers-derived databases), telomere orientation (+ for inward and - for outward repeats with >100 occurrences) from QuarTeT, and gap count from Detgaps.

Scaffold_name	Length	QV_k21	Errors_k21	QV_k31	Errors_k31	Left_telomere	Gaps	Right_telomere
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	Mb.	21-mer	21-mer	31-mer	31-mer	(5' AACCCCT)	(N)	(AGGGTT 3')
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_01	51,1	64.5442	377	59.4881	1783	119 (+)	T2T	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_02	51,7	56.0219	2713	56.0911	3942	174 (+)	1	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_03	47,6	59.3028	1174	54.5941	5125	1701 (+)	3	1603 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_04	44,3	49.4714	10490	56.9825	2716	185 (+)	8	160 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_05	41,5	62.5139	488	61.5864	892	1472 (+)	T2T	1883 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_06	41,3	54.5824	3021	56.2081	3068	278 (+)	1	1447 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_07	42,6	58.0864	1389	54.3111	4889	384 (+)	3	382 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_08	40,2	54.3182	3124	59.8602	1287	0	T2T	130 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_09	37,3	55.9044	2013	53.8378	4784	1449 (+)	1	315 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_10	34,9	67.6478	126	60.3736	993	0	2	127 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_11	33,5	51.4996	4986	58.2486	1555	1614 (+)	T2T	1997 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_12	35,3	54.4649	2653	58.1993	1657	0	6	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_13	33,6	66.4695	159	63.3235	483	1525 (+)	2	1557 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_14	32,4	47.2905	12717	61.6029	690	105 (+)	T2T	226 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_15	35	64.2407	275	58.2795	1602	328 (+)	2	118 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_16	33,8	60.5363	627	57.9679	1675	1602 (+)	4	137 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_17	30,3	55.2666	1892	56.604	2052	335 (-)	T2T	276 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_18	30,5	56.641	1382	57.9088	1522	1411 (+)	3	2289 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_19	30,7	64.5469	226	58.6026	1311	784 (+)	2	178 (+)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_20	27,1	57.0276	1128	60.0252	835	171 (+)	2	406 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_21	30,6	60.6832	549	60.1377	919	1936 (+)	2	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_22	30	62.328	369	60.2163	886	0	2	129 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_23	26,2	52.9697	2773	58.0814	1260	279 (+)	1	1739 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_24	25,9	60.3587	501	60.6659	689	185 (+)	2	114 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_25	25,6	58.5637	748	59.0404	989	232 (+)	T2T	129 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_26	26,3	56.7889	1163	57.358	1506	1343 (+)	3	0
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_27	24	68.2243	76	59.5233	832	0	T2T	264 (-)
fClaHyb_african_1_Chromosome_28	20,3	59.8335	443	56.9713	1261	0	2	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_01	50,1	55.7992	2767	50.7048	13207	998 (+)	14	740 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_02	44,3	51.8276	6102	54.4421	4934	815 (+)	5	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_03	40,4	44.33	31251	55.4715	3531	327 (+)	12	279 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_04	38,4	52.1302	4933	52.1322	7281	222 (+)	13	819 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_05	38,1	47.0334	15835	53.7219	4994	321 (+)	14	301 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_06	37,4	52.5469	4370	50.6785	9921	282 (+)	14	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_07	33,8	50.998	5644	48.4795	14888	924 (+)	15	629 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_08	45,6	56.2767	2252	51.0889	10984	161 (+)	11	1237 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_09	30	48.1331	9677	48.5674	12936	184 (+)	13	751 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_10	29,8	54.8059	2065	49.5164	10314	316 (+)	12	664 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_11	25	51.0866	4085	53.4888	3469	0	21	267 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_12	31,6	48.5768	9241	47.4853	17546	559 (+)	13	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_13	24,9	44.8933	16909	48.6904	10418	740 (+)	8	220 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_14	23,3	44.5272	17249	51.8503	4715	0	8	190 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_15	27,6	39.2488	68816	52.3266	4848	200 (+)	12	107 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_16	25,2	51.936	3389	53.2655	3686	656 (+)	9	818 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_17	24	40.0722	49568	46.7745	15616	326 (+)	15	222 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_18	25,2	52.6726	2856	52.3131	4582	632 (+)	11	973 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_19	31,1	53.8536	2692	52.9809	4841	674 (+)	8	751 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_20	32,7	51.6697	4681	51.0227	7929	410 (+)	18	422 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_21	29,2	43.0312	30479	51.9822	5662	805 (+)	16	253 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_22	34,9	51.0828	5705	50.9355	8715	568 (+)	13	121 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_23	31,7	42.7592	35295	48.8582	12797	931 (+)	8	1022 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_24	29,6	50.1103	6080	52.8055	4829	851 (+)	10	159 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_25	40,3	52.391	4875	52.1653	7582	0	9	798 (-)
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_26	40,1	53.1914	4035	51.6319	8529	1038 (+)	11	0
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chromosome_27	30,5	48.7036	8641	48.5145	13324	1858 (+)	10	219 (-)

Table 2. Summary of structural accuracy metrics of scaffolds of haplotype-resolved genome assembly of Hybrid catfish. Structural accuracy (S-AQI, %), Regional accuracy (R-AQI %), heterozygous regions (Avg.CSH /Avg.CRH) from CRAQ.

Scaffold_name	Mapping.rate	Avg.CRH	Avg.CRE	Avg.CSE	Regional-AQI	Avg.CSH	Structural-AQI
Sub-Genome_Chromosome	ONT/PE (%)	Count	Count	Count	Accuracy (%)	Count	Accuracy (%)
Genome (55 Chromosomes)	>97%	0.046	0.270	0.021	97.33	0.001	97.92
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_01	0.992	0.020	0.078	0.000	99.22	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_02	0.981	0.000	0.098	0.000	99.02	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_03	0.955	0.033	0.154	0.000	98.47	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_04	0.980	0.046	0.207	0.046	97.95	0.000	95.50
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_05	0.986	0.048	0.097	0.000	99.04	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_06	0.998	0.024	0.085	0.000	99.15	0.024	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_07	0.978	0.000	0.120	0.000	98.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_08	0.992	0.025	0.100	0.000	99.00	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_09	0.992	0.076	0.083	0.027	99.17	0.000	97.34
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_10	0.998	0.066	0.172	0.000	98.29	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_11	0.905	0.030	0.188	0.000	98.13	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_12	0.873	0.086	0.230	0.000	97.72	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_13	0.917	0.075	0.119	0.000	98.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_14	0.990	0.031	0.062	0.062	99.38	0.000	93.96
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_15	0.922	0.076	0.152	0.000	98.49	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_16	0.952	0.000	0.248	0.000	97.55	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_17	0.997	0.033	0.083	0.000	99.18	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_18	0.954	0.175	0.315	0.000	96.90	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_19	0.998	0.000	0.294	0.033	97.10	0.000	96.79
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_20	0.995	0.056	0.148	0.000	98.53	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_21	0.986	0.033	0.131	0.098	98.70	0.000	90.65
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_22	0.992	0.067	0.134	0.034	98.67	0.000	96.70
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_23	0.998	0.058	0.186	0.038	98.16	0.000	96.23
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_24	0.999	0.077	0.232	0.000	97.71	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_25	0.989	0.039	0.118	0.000	98.83	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_26	0.994	0.057	0.324	0.000	96.81	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_27	0.980	0.042	0.166	0.000	98.35	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_african_1_Chrom_28	0.995	0.000	0.297	0.000	97.07	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_01	0.981	0.000	0.329	0.000	96.76	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_02	0.992	0.046	0.148	0.023	98.53	0.000	97.75
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_03	0.980	0.050	0.276	0.000	97.28	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_04	0.990	0.000	0.370	0.026	96.36	0.000	97.40
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_05	0.972	0.053	0.360	0.160	96.46	0.000	85.22
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_06	0.934	0.000	0.497	0.027	95.15	0.000	97.33
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_07	0.990	0.030	0.403	0.030	96.05	0.000	97.06
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_08	0.987	0.000	0.429	0.044	95.80	0.000	95.66
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_09	0.986	0.051	0.422	0.067	95.87	0.000	93.47
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_10	0.982	0.034	0.460	0.034	95.50	0.000	96.65
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_11	0.961	0.042	0.382	0.042	96.26	0.000	95.92
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_12	0.946	0.194	0.606	0.069	94.12	0.000	93.38
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_13	0.989	0.041	0.509	0.081	95.04	0.000	92.19
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_14	0.982	0.080	0.544	0.000	94.71	0.044	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_15	0.922	0.136	0.506	0.039	95.07	0.000	96.19
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_16	0.993	0.040	0.240	0.000	97.63	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_17	0.985	0.042	0.793	0.042	92.38	0.000	95.87
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_18	0.977	0.000	0.474	0.000	95.37	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_19	0.992	0.000	0.341	0.000	96.65	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_20	0.971	0.000	0.236	0.062	97.66	0.000	93.96
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_21	0.977	0.064	0.591	0.000	94.26	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_22	0.935	0.102	0.406	0.044	96.02	0.000	95.74
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_23	0.990	0.000	0.303	0.032	97.02	0.000	96.87
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_24	0.992	0.303	0.608	0.000	94.10	0.000	100.00
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_25	0.990	0.062	0.350	0.025	96.56	0.000	97.53
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_26	0.991	0.050	0.378	0.025	96.29	0.000	97.51
fClaHyb_bighead_1_Chrom_27	0.979	0.033	0.447	0.000	95.63	0.000	100.00

Figure 3. North African catfish subgenome synteny and structural variation summary. Reference: GCA_024256425.2_CGAR_prim_01v2_genomic; Query: GCA_048129225.1_fClahyb_Gar_genomic. Barplots summarise SNP, insertion, deletion, and structural variant counts and genome fractions.

Figure 4. Bighead catfish subgenome synteny and structural variation summary. Reference: GCA_048544425.1_fClMac1.0_hap1_genomic; Query: GCA_048129245.1_fClHyb_Mac_genomic. Barplots summarise SNP, insertion, deletion, and structural variant counts and genome fractions.

Figure 5. Conceptual framework of F1 hybrid catfish genome structure and its role in population restoration. The diagram illustrates pure parental species (F0) with high genome divergence (>5%) producing F1 hybrids via hybridization. F1 hybrids retain unmixed haploid subgenomes, function as genetic reservoirs of parental alleles, and exhibit heterosis driven by gene dosage and morphogen gradient effects, resulting in phenotypes with incomplete-to-complete dominance. Subsequent generations (F2+) show limited genome mixing, while higher generations (F3+) experience synaptogenesis anomalies and unbalanced centromere composition leading to developmental failure and sterility, rendering backcrossing extremely rare. This framework highlights the utility of F1 hybrids in restoring pure species within genetically stressed populations.

